

Separation of lactic acid from fermented residual resources using membrane technology

Eleftheria Papadopoulou^{b,1}, Mayuki Cabrera González^{a,1}, Daniela Reif^{c,*}, Amal Ahmed^a, Panagiotis Tsapekos^b, Irini Angelidaki^b, Michael Harasek^a

^a Institute of Chemical, Environmental and Bioscience Engineering, TU Wien, Getreidemarkt 9, Vienna 1060, Austria

^b Department of Chemical and Biochemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Kongens Lyngby DK-2800, Denmark

^c Institute for Water Quality and Resource Management, TU Wien, Vienna 1040, Austria

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Dr Y Liu

Keywords:

Lactic acid
Organic waste
Microfiltration
Nanofiltration
Electrodialysis

ABSTRACT

Lactic acid can be derived from microbial fermentation and be used as a platform chemical in various industrial applications. This study aims to investigate the challenges involved in combining a low-cost, heterogeneous feedstock, such as a mixture of candy-waste and digestate, with an optimized downstream strategy to achieve maximum recovery of high-purity lactic acid, targeting low energy consumption. To achieve this goal, four membrane separation technologies, namely microfiltration, nanofiltration, monopolar, and bipolar electro dialysis, were combined to design two purification processes. Microfiltration served as the pre-purification step, followed by either process A, which combined nanofiltration and bipolar electro dialysis, or process B, a combination of monopolar and bipolar electro dialysis. The findings emphasized the importance of pH as a control factor. Nanofiltration at pH 2.8 and monopolar electro dialysis at pH 4.0 led to increased lactic acid recovery. Moreover, it was observed that process B resulted in 1.09-fold higher lactic acid recovery than process A. However, process A had a 1.19-fold lower specific energy consumption, and the presence of ions in the final solution was reduced by 5-fold. In both processes lactic acid was separated from sugars and organic acids. Overall, the findings of this study suggest that membrane separation technology is a viable method for separating lactic acid produced from a mixture of residual candy-waste and digestate.

1. Introduction

Climate data show that the Earth's surface temperature has increased by 1 °C since the start of the industrial revolution, with 2022 being the sixth-warmest year on record [11]. Meanwhile, the human population has tripled compared to the mid-20th century [32], leading to overconsumption and overexploitation of natural resources in producing sufficient energy, fuels, and chemicals [31]. To achieve a greener transition, biorefinery technologies are being developed to valorize biomass to produce bio-energy, bio-fuels, and bio-chemicals [18].

Lactic acid is a bio-chemical mainly generated through microbial fermentation with the application of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) [5]. It is used as a platform chemical for generating products appearing in various sectors, such as food or medical industries [6]. The main factors decreasing the production cost of lactic acid for scaled-up processes are a. the use of an inexpensive substrate with low pretreatment

requirements [15], b. the use of a robust microorganism resistant to adverse conditions and fermentation products [5], and c. the optimization of separation and purification strategies.

The most widely used inexpensive biomass for lactic acid production is the lignocellulosic material from agriculture [2] or forest residues [35]. However, the presence of lignin creates the need for pretreatment, increasing the total operational cost [16]. In the search of biomass with low lignin content, organic waste is suggested [3]. Using organic municipal and industrial residues in biorefinery systems creates new value from what was previously considered waste. Meanwhile, the use of organic residues as fermentation resources is suggested as a waste management approach [3]. For example, lactic acid has been produced in a yield of 0.75 g_{LA} g⁻¹_{sugars} and productivity of 1.09 g L⁻¹ h⁻¹ by source-sorted organic household waste [36], and a yield of 0.98 g_{LA} g⁻¹_{sugars}, and productivity of 1.33 g L⁻¹ h⁻¹ by hydrolyzed cheese whey as carbohydrate sources [38].

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: dreif@iwag.tuwien.ac.at (D. Reif).

¹ Eleftheria Papadopoulou and Mayuki Cabrera González have contributed equally to this work.

The downstream strategy should be planned considering the heterogeneity and characteristics of the specific biological substrate. Membrane separation is suggested as a green methodology among other downstream processes as harmful chemicals are not applied, and it is easily up-scaled [1]. Microfiltration (MF) is used for the separation of molecules with molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) > 10,000 Da, such as microbial biomass [1], and nanofiltration (NF) is introduced for molecule separation with MWCO 200–1000 Da [20], such as proteins, macromolecules, and multivalent anions [1,8]. The amount of dissociated lactic acid in the substrate strongly affects nanofiltration. The dissociation constant of lactic acid or pK_a is 3.86 at 25 °C [28]. The use of membranes was the first lactic acid purification step applied on fermentation broths deriving from coffee mucilage [24], or from organic fraction of municipal solid waste [21]. The filtration conditions fluctuate depending on the characteristics of the specific substrates.

Electrodialysis (ED) is another membrane separation technology which has received significant attention for the concentration and purification of organic acids [12]. Monopolar ED (MED) is a methodology that utilizes an electric field on ion exchange membranes to concentrate organic acids [12,22]. Bipolar membrane electrodialysis (BPED) is an alternative ED method, where monopolar membranes are combined with bipolar membranes to produce acids and bases from salts (C. [19]. Using BPED, sodium lactate can be converted to lactic acid and sodium hydroxide. In a study conducted by Olszewska et al. [25], lactic acid was produced from sweet sorghum juice, concentrated by MED, and further converted with BPED. In total, 85.6% of the initial lactic acid could be recovered. In another study [27], lactic acid was produced using mixed restaurant food waste as a substrate, and a combination of MF, NF, ED, chromatography, and distillation were applied to recover 38% of the initial lactic acid amount.

Overall, the separation efficiency and the energy consumption of membrane processes depend on the supernatant composition influenced by the applied feedstock media. This study employed a lactic acid solution produced by microbial fermentation of a mixed substrate consisting of candy-waste and digestate that has not been studied before. In lab-scale experiments, two process routes have been compared and evaluated to maximize lactic acid recovery and purity, and minimize energy consumption. Process A consisted of prefiltration with MF and NF followed by conversion of lactate to lactic acid in BPED. Process B included pretreatment with MF and MED and subsequent BPED.

03 2. Materials and methods

2.1. Model solution and chemical reagents

A model solution was used for the preliminary experiments, which aimed at maximizing the LA recovery during NF and MED treatment. The solution was formulated based on the properties of the biological MF permeate, which contained 13.70 g L⁻¹ maltose, 0.10 g L⁻¹ glucose, 0.10 g L⁻¹, succinic acid, 34.31 g L⁻¹ lactic acid, and 0.20 g L⁻¹ acetic acid. Analytical grade chemicals (Sigma- Aldrich, Darmstadt, Deutschland) were used, and NaCl (99.0%) was added to adjust the conductivity, while HCl (99.8%) or NaOH (98.0%) was used to adjust the pH.

2.2. Biological substrate

The biological substrate (Table 1) was prepared and obtained from the Chemical Engineering Department, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark. The fermentation broth was produced by co-fermenting digestate from a full-scale biogas plant (Hashøj biogas plant, Dalmose, Denmark) and candy-factory waste (*Trolli Ibérica A/S*, Paterna, Spain) and *Lactobacillus plantarum* as seed, in 5-L bioreactors (BioBench, Biostream International BV, Doetinchem, The Netherlands). The substrate selection, pre-treatment, choice of bacterial seed, and fermentation process were previously described by Papadopoulou et al. [26]. The substrate was centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 15 min at 4 °C to

Table 1

Characteristics of the initial fermentation broth diluted 1:1 with distilled water at pH 6.5.

Parameters	Biological sample (g L ⁻¹)
Total solids (TS)	38.10 ± 0.51
Volatile solids (VS)	23.61 ± 0.24
Glucose	n.d.
Sucrose	n.d.
Maltose	19.55 ± 1.60
Lactic acid	31.30 ± 1.81
Succinic acid	0.30 ± 0.30
Formic acid	n.d.
Acetic acid	0.77 ± 0.52

n.d.: not detected.

remove coarse particles, and the liquid fraction was stored at - 20 °C. Before the membrane separation, the biological substrate was thawed, diluted 1:1 with distilled water, and homogenized for 30 min to increase permeability.

2.3. Pressure-driven membrane separation process

MF was applied at a laboratory-scale flow unit (OS-MC-01 OSMO Membrane Systems, H. Korntal-Münchingen, Germany) with a 2-L unit tank operated at low pressure. The unit was equipped with a 0.008 m² (0.04 m × 0.2 m) membrane module and a flat sheet MFG2 membrane (Alfa Laval, Lund, Sweden) (Table 2). The system temperature was controlled using a circulating bath (PolyScience 9706A12E Refrigerated/Heated, Manchester, UK) at 60 °C. The process resulted in two streams: a MF retentate (30% of the feed), which was discarded, and a MF permeate (70% of the feed). The MF permeate was further processed using NF. NF was conducted in the same cross-flow unit at room temperature and low feed pressure. The unit was equipped with a flat sheet NF245 membrane (FilmTech™, United States) (Table 2). Similar to MF, two streams were produced, a NF retentate (30% of the feed) which was discarded, and a NF permeate (70% of the feed), where lactic acid was accumulated.

In both membrane separation processes, conductivity and pH were monitored every 30 min using the multi-parameter pH-meter VWR pHMenal® MU 6100 (WR International, Vienna, Austria), (Fig. S2). The permeate was determined by measuring and recording the permeate mass every 60 min for MF and 25 min for NF using a laboratory precision balance (Kern PKP 4200–2, Precision 0.01 g / max, 4210 g, Reinach, Switzerland). All experiments were performed in batch mode in duplicate, except for NF experiments.

2.4. Electrodialysis

MED and BPED tests were performed in batch mode using the BED 1–3 64004 (PCCell GmbH, Germany) system. The system consisted of an electrolyte stack with ten cell pairs and an effective membrane area of 0.0064 m². For MED, monovalent selective anion-exchange membrane (AEM) and monovalent selective cation-exchange membrane (CEM) were used. The spacer thickness was 0.45 mm. PC MTE cation exchange membranes were used as end membranes. For BPED, bipolar membranes (PCCell GmbH, Germany) were included in the stack. Specifications of the membranes are listed in Table 3. The system had three external double-wall tanks for dilute/ concentrate or feed/ acid/ base and an internal reservoir for the electrolyte rinse solution. The electrolyte rinse solution was 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ and circulated in the system at a flow rate of 15 L h⁻¹. The flow rate of the system for both MED and BPED processes was set at 15 L h⁻¹. The maximum current and voltage that could be applied were 5 A and 30 V, respectively. The voltage remained constant at 30 V, whereas a low current value of 0.4 A (current density: 62.5 A m⁻²) was applied if either

Table 2

Membrane characteristics, where MF: microfiltration; NF: nanofiltration; experiments.

Flat Sheet Membrane type	Model	Manufacturer	Material	pH rangeRef. 25 °C	Pore Size-MWCO	Max Temp. (°C)	Max P (bar)
MF	MFG2	Alga Laval	Polypropylene	1.5–12	0.2 µm	75	3
NF	NF245	DOW™	Polyamide-TFC	1.0–10	300 Da	50	54.8

Table 3

Properties of the membranes used for MED: Monopolar electro dialysis; BPED: Bipolar electro dialysis experiments.

	Membrane	Type	Functional Group	Thickness (µm)	Resistance (Ω cm ²)	Transfer number	pH stability
Monopolar electro dialysis	PC MTE	CEM	Sulfonic acid	220	4.5	> 0.94	1–8
	PC MVA	AEM	Ammonium	110	20	> 0.97	0–9
	PC MVK	CEM	Sulfonic acid	100	n.a.	> 0.97	0–10
Bipolar electro dialysis	PC MTE	CEM	Sulfonic acid	220	4.5	> 0.94	1–8
	PC acid 60	AEM	Ammonium	100–110	2	> 0.95	0–9
	PC SK	CEM	sulfonic acid	100–120	2.5	> 0.95	0–11
	PC bip	BP	bipolar	200–350	-	> 0.95*	0–12

n.a.: not available.

* Water-splitting efficiency

concentrate or dilute electrical conductivity (EC) was below 5 mS cm⁻¹. The applied current densities (CD) were selected based on prior experiments and were approximately 50% of the LCD (Limiting Current Density) obtained at these concentration levels (Fig. S3). However, if the EC of both streams was above 5 mS cm⁻¹, a higher value of 0.7 A (110 A m⁻²) was used. All experiments were finalized when an EC of 5 mS cm⁻¹ was achieved in the feed solution. EC, temperature, and pH were continuously monitored and recorded (Fig. S2). All experiments were performed in duplicate. The experimental time, specific energy demand, and lactic acid recovery were considered during the evaluation of experimental results.

2.5. Experimental set-up

To achieve maximum recovery of high-purity lactic acid while minimizing energy consumption, selected membrane processes were optimized (Table 4). The factor studied and controlled was the pH, which affects both NF and MED methods. The pK_a of lactic acid was estimated to be 3.86 at 25 °C [28]. Considering this information, three pH conditions were tested to investigate how the dissociation of lactic acid affects the separation by membrane technology. Therefore, pH 4.0 was selected as a value close to the dissociation constant, while pH 2.8, a value lower than the pK_a, was chosen based on a previous study [8], which indicated that it was the optimal pH for lactic acid separation following the NF process. All three pH conditions were evaluated for affecting the MED process, utilizing the model solution. However, only two pH conditions, pH 2.8 and 6.5, were applied for the NF process, as previous research on the separation of model lactic acid solution [8] demonstrated that these two values exhibited the greatest differences. The initial pH of the model solutions, which was approximately 2.0, was

Table 4

Experimental design for the optimization of the lactic acid downstream process.

Separation method	Substrate	Pressure (bar)	Temperature (C)	pH	Current (A)	Voltage (V)
MF	Biological diluted 1:1	2	60	6.5	-	-
NF	MF permeate	28	25	2.8	-	-
MED	Synthetic	-	22.17 ± 0.80	6.5	0.7	30
				2.8		
				4.0		
MC	MF permeate	-	22.85 ± 0.65	n.a.	-	-
	Synthetic		23.29 ± 1.01	n.a.		
BPED	NF permeate	-	24.75 ± 0.15	n.a.	0.4	30
	MED concentrate		24.05 ± 1.05	n.a.	0.7	30

n.a.: Not available.

adjusted by adding NaOH until the desired pH (2.8, 4.0, or 6.5) was obtained. NaCl was added to reach an equal EC of 15 mS cm⁻¹ for all the solutions, representing the EC of the original fermentation effluent. Initially, the dilute container was filled with 400 mL of the test solution, while the concentrate was filled with 400 mL of deionized water.

Additionally, fed-batch experiments were conducted at pH 4.0 with a model solution to increase the purity and concentration of the lactic acid solution. Diluate and concentrate containers were filled with 400 mL of lactic acid model solution and deionized water. After the first batch experiment, the diluate was replaced with a new model solution while reusing the obtained concentrate. In total, three fed-batch experiments were performed in duplicate. The experimental time, specific energy demand, and LA recovery were considered for the evaluation of the results.

Experiments with biological samples were conducted as a validation step to determine the best process design (Fig. 1). First, the fermentation broth was diluted 1:1 with distilled water to allow permeability through the membrane, and it was used as a feed for the pre-purification step. The MF permeate was then used either in process A, as a feed for either NF or in process B, as feed for MED, operating at the selected pH found in the preliminary experiments. The NF permeate, and the MED concentrate were tested as feed solutions for BPED.

2.6. Analytical methods

Sugars (maltose and glucose) and organic acids (lactic, succinic, and acetic) were detected and measured with High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). The HPLC unit was equipped with a refractive detector and a Shodex SH1011 (8.0 mm × 300 mm) column, operating at a column oven temperature of 60 °C. Eluent was 5 mM H₂SO₄, and

Fig. 1. Experimental set-up for maximum lactic acid recovery and purity.

analysis was conducted with a 0.6 mL min^{-1} flow rate. Before the analysis, the samples were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatant was diluted with distilled water. The samples were filtered with non-sterile $0.22 \mu\text{m}$ pore size filters (Dissolution accessories, Munich, Germany) into the glass vials.

Anions (chloride, sulfate) and cations (sodium, potassium, calcium, and magnesium) were analyzed according to DIN EN ISO 14911 by HPLC. The limit of quantification (LOQ)/limit of detection (LOD) was $0.5/0.2 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ for anions and $0.8/0.4 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ for cations.

3. Calculations

3.1. Lactic acid recovery and purity

Lactic acid recovery (R) (Eq. 1), and purity (P) (Eq. 2) were calculated as yields for all separation strategies.

$$R(\%) = \left(\frac{M_p^{LA}}{M_f^{LA}} \right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$P(\%) = \left(\frac{M_p^{LA}}{M_p} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where: M_p^{LA} – mass of lactic acid in the permeate or in the diluate for filtration and ED strategies, accordingly; M_f^{LA} – mass of lactic acid in the feed; M_p – mass of sugars and organic acids recovered after downstream.

3.2. Microfiltration and Nanofiltration

The pump power (Eq. 3) and the final volume of the permeate were considered for the calculation of the specific energy consumption (SEC) (Eq. 4). Pump power is characterized as the pressure needed to pump the feed in the system.

$$P_p = \frac{Q_{Uf} \times P_U}{\eta} \quad (3)$$

$$SEC = \frac{P_p}{Q_{Up}} \quad (4)$$

Where P_p : pump power (W), Q_{Uf} : feed flow ($\text{m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), P_U : pressure ($\text{Kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), η : pump efficiency (0.75), Q_{Up} : permeate flow ($\text{m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

In the MF process, the energy consumption for the temperature control of the thermal bath was also considered (Eq. 5). The temperature of the system was set at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

$$Q = m \times c \times \Delta T$$

Where m : mass (kg), c : specific water heat ($4.180 \times 10^3 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$), ΔT :

temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$).

The capacity of the circulating bath was 13-L capacity but only 3 L were used for heating.

3.3. Electrodialysis

The electrical power $P_{ED,t}$ and cumulative electrical energy demand E_{ED} were calculated according to Eq. 6, and Eq. 7.

$$P_{ED,t} = U_t \times I_t \quad (6)$$

$$E_{ED} = \sum_{n=0}^t P_{ED,t} \times (t_{n+1} - t_n) \quad (7)$$

Where: U_t – recorded voltage; I_t – applied current; t – desalination time.

Power for pumping P_p was calculated based on Eq. 8. The observed pressure drop was approximately 0.5 bar at a chosen flow velocity of 15 L h^{-1} for the feed, concentrate/acid and base pump, and 120 L h^{-1} for the electrolyte pump.

$$P_p = V \times \rho \times \Delta p \quad (8)$$

where: V – volume flow; Δp – pressure-drop; ρ – density of the water matrix.

The energy demand for pumping E_p was the product of pumping power, time, and n the number of pumps needed (diluate pump, concentrate pump, base pump/electrolyte pump) divided by the pump efficiency (assumed with $\eta = 0.8$) and described in Eq. 9.

$$E_p = \frac{P_p \times t \times n}{\eta} \quad (9)$$

The total cumulative energy demand E_{total} is the sum of the electrical energy demand for desalination and the energy demand for pumping (Eq. 10). SEC was also calculated according to Eq. 4.

$$E_{total} = E_{ED} + E_p \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, the recovery efficiency of lactic acid (RE_{LA}) was assessed using initial and final masses within the diluate compartment (Eq. 11).

$$RE_{LA} = 1 - \frac{m_{D,i}^0 - m_{D,i}^f}{m_{D,i}^0} \times 100 \quad (11)$$

where: $\lambda_{D,i}^0, \lambda_{D,i}^f$ – the initial and final EC (mS cm^{-1}) of the feed solution; $m_{D,i}^0, m_{D,i}^f$ – initial and final mass in the diluate compartment.

4. Results and discussion

To determine the optimal downstream process for achieving maximum recovery of high-purity lactic acid from a fermentation broth

derived from a mixture of residual streams, two membrane processes were designed. Firstly, the pH was tested and optimized as a factor that could potentially influence the separation of lactic acid during the implementation of NF or MED technology. Subsequently, MF was applied as a pre-purification step and two downstream processes were suggested. Process A involved a NF step followed by BPED, while process B combined MED and BPED. Finally, a fed-batch MED operation was examined as a method for up-concentration of lactic acid.

4.1. Effect of NF and MED processes

Two sets of NF experiments were conducted to investigate the influence of pH on lactic acid separation process. In the first set the pH of the biological substrate remained unchanged at 6.5, whereas in the second case the pH was reduced to 2.8. When the pH was 6.5, 27.22% lactic acid was recovered, and 3.58% of maltose was found in the permeate (Fig. 2). Altering the pH to 2.8 led to a 1.64-fold increase in lactic acid recovery, but also a 3.70-fold higher amount of maltose was recovered, reducing the purity of lactic acid.

The pH of the feed solution in NF processes has been reported to affect the charge of the membrane, which is dependent on the membrane's isoelectric point. For instance, research has shown that the isoelectric point of a 5 membrane, which was also used in this study, is close to 4.0 [7]. At pH levels higher than 4.0 the membrane becomes negatively charged. As lactic acid is also negatively charged, a greater amount of lactate is detected and retained in the retentate, instead of being recovered in the permeate.

The recovery rate of lactic acid separated from the biological substrate in the selected pH ranges was comparable to the results previously reported by Cabrera-González et al. [8], operating also in laboratory scale, using a model solution of lactic acid. According to their research, lactic acid recovery rates ranged from 0% to 20% at pH 6.0, while at pH 2.8 the recovery rates increased to ranges between 29% and 93%, depending on the characteristics of the employed membranes.

However, a study presented by Alexandri et al. [1] demonstrated a fermentation process using residue substrates, combined with NF as downstream technology, resulting in lactic acid recovery yields ranging from 77.6% to 97.5%. In contrast, the sugar recovery rates were found to be in the range of 63–100%, similar to those achieved in the current study. The variation in lactic acid recovery rate observed between the two studies can be attributed to several factors, including differences in membrane area, substrate composition, and membrane characteristics. An important distinction between the two studies, is that Alexandri et al. [1], conducted NF experiments on a pilot scale, utilizing a membrane area that was 213-fold larger than the one used in the current study.

Furthermore, disparities in substrate composition between the two studies could also play a role. Alexandri et al. [1] employed residue substrates with an average disaccharide concentration that was 1.9-fold lower compared to the samples used in the present study. Such differences in substrate composition can impact the performance of the membrane separation process. Finally, variations in the characteristics of the membranes utilized in the two studies may also contribute to the differences in lactic acid recovery rates. These differences could arise due to membrane permeability, selectivity, or surface charge, which can affect the separation efficiency.

An additional contributing factor to the decrease in the reported lactic acid amount was the presence of process losses, constituting approximately 18.53% of the initial mass, regardless of the chosen pH. Process losses have been previously observed and reported [4]. However, in this specific study, the percentage of process losses appears to be higher compared to the previously reported range of 6–7%. Despite this difference, the consistency of these process losses was observed throughout the repeated experiments.

The effect of pH on the MED process was also studied, and the results (Fig. 2) indicated that lactic acid recovery was highest at pH 4.0, with a 1.05-fold increase compared to pH 2.8 and 6.0. Additionally, the experimental time, electrical, pumping, and electrical energy demand decreased with increasing pH value (Table 5). These results could be attributed to the fact that when the pH of the feed is lower than 3.86, lactic acid will remain undissociated in the diluate compartment [28]. Conversely, if the pH is regulated at higher values, the lactate anion will mitigate in the concentrate compartment. In a previous study on removing lactic acid from acid whey [10], no significant differences were found in lactic acid removal and specific energy consumption between pH 4.6 and 6.0 at temperatures between 30 and 45 °C. However, the present study discovered that at pH 6.0, the specific energy

Table 5
Energy characteristics for different pH conditions applied on monopolar electro dialysis (MED) technology.

pH	Initial volume diluate (L)	ΔEC_d ($mS\ cm^{-1}$)	Exp. Time (h)	Electrical energy (Wh)	Pumping energy (Wh)	Specific energy demand ($kWh\ m^{-3}$)
2.8	0.289 ± 0.015	13.13 ± 0.14	1.74 ± 0.01	11.6 ± 0.4	1.8 ± 0.0	46.6 ± 2.1
4	0.292 ± 0.177	15.18 ± 3.10	1.17 ± 0.02	9.5 ± 0.3	1.2 ± 0.0	36.8 ± 3.1
6.5	0.308 ± 0.092	13.99 ± 0.45	0.96 ± 0.07	7.1 ± 0.7	1.0 ± 0.1	26.2 ± 0.5

Fig. 2. pH effect on nanofiltration (NF) and monopolar electro dialysis (MED) technologies. Plot a. shows the lactic acid recovery (%) in each studied pH and plot b. shows the fluctuation of electric conductivity (EC) in the diluate and the concentrate, in different pH values.

consumption was 1.4 times lower than in pH 4.0. In general, the more dissociated the lactic acid, the less energy is required to separate lactic acid into ion form, most of the energy is used to facilitate ion transfer [28]. Considering both the high lactic acid recovery and the reduction in energy demand, the pH of 4.0 was selected to continue with the MED experiments.

26-27
2 notes

28

4.2. Maximum recovery of high-purity lactic acid using membrane separation technologies

The fermentation broth utilized in this study was derived from a co-fermentation of candy-waste and digestate. Candy-factory residues contain impurities of high molecular weight, such as gelatin and sugars [17]. The addition of high sugar concentration in gelatin systems has been found to increase the initial melting point of gelatin ($\approx 35^\circ\text{C}$) (R. [34]). Thus, to decrease the viscosity and turbidity of the substrate, a first MF separation step with MF filters was proposed as a common pre-purification step [17]. Furthermore, to minimize a potential flux reduction caused by gelling behaviour of the substrate, the tank temperature was set at 60°C . The applied temperature was not optimized.

29

30

31

The results (Table 6, Fig. 3) demonstrate that the MF technique allowed for the recovery of $73.27 \pm 1.07\%$ of the compounds present in the fermentation broth. The average purity of lactic acid obtained was $59.20 \pm 2.63\%$. The lactic acid losses observed here are comparable with previous findings involving heterogeneous substrate, such as crust bread [1]. However, the observed losses were higher by 1.15- to 1.36-fold when compared to other substrates such as sugar bread and acid whey, respectively. The variability in rejection rates among different substrates, as discussed by Alexandri et al. [1], suggests that substrate characteristics play a significant role in influencing lactic acid loss during the MF process.

32

33-34
2 notes

Furthermore, the permeate flux for MF was also monitored, and it exhibited a decrease over time, with a 13.5% reduction observed after 3 h (Fig. S1). This phenomenon can be attributed to membrane fouling from the fermentation broth [1]. Cross-flow MF, as the one applied in this study, is known for effectively controlling the disposition of bacterial cells to the membrane surface, resulting in a relatively constant permeate flux of $37 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ [29], which is consistent with the one obtained in this study.

35

Finally, the SEC for the process was calculated to be 0.10 kWh m^{-3} . Comparatively a typical MF process requires 0.18 kWh to produce 1 m^3

of water [30]. In a previous study by Najid et al. [23] the SEC was estimated to be nearly constant at approximately 0.086 kWh m^{-3} , which is comparable to the results presented in this study.

Subsequently, NF permeate was directed either for NF at pH 2.8, or MED at pH 4.0. Results (Fig. 3) showed when MED was used, 2.14-fold more lactic acid was recovered, and purity was 1.15-fold higher than that obtained with the NF process. Moreover, when NF was used, 3.09-fold more maltose was recovered. However, the SEC for MED was 23-fold higher than that for NF. Both technologies achieved decolorization of the permeate and concentrate, respectively (Fig. S4). This aligns with literature reporting high decolorization rates achieved by nanofiltration membranes [9]. During MED experiments, the concentrate tank was initially filled with deionized water. Macromolecular compounds such as pigments and proteins are retained via the high selectivity of IEX membranes and will rather remain in the diluate compartments due to the small membrane pore sizes ($<1 \text{ nm}$) [37].

The application of BPED to the NF permeate or MED concentrate resulted in the complete separation of lactic acid from residual sugars and organic acids in the fermentation broth. The recovery of lactic acid was 1.09-fold higher when MED concentrate was used as BPED feed compared to the NF permeate. On the other hand, the combination of NF and BPED reduced the specific energy consumption of the process by 4.54-fold, compared to the combination of MED and BPED (Table 7). In a similar study conducted by Knežević et al. [14] NF, MED, and ion-exchange membranes were applied for ion removal from fermentation eluent, before the application of BPED. The energy demand calculated for NF was 1.06 kWh m^{-3} , which is comparable with the present study. However, the energy demand recorded for MED in this study almost 2.5-times higher than the one reported from Knežević et al. deviation could be attributed to the fact that in the study of Knežević et al., the current density was almost half compared to the one applied in this study.

Regarding ion concentration (Table 6), it was detected that the MED concentrate contained 3.07-fold more ions than the NF permeate. After the BPED process, 6.02-fold more ions were detected in Process B than in Process A. These findings were also supported by the calculation of the ion removal efficiencies obtained during the applied ED processes on the biological sample (Table S1). According to the results, in process A, complete removal of SO_4^{2-} and K^+ ions was achieved, while Cl^- and Na^+ ions were partially removed by $93.74 \pm 1.88\%$ and $90.36 \pm 2.32\%$, respectively. The removal efficiency of lactic acid from the diluate

Table 6

Concentration of organic acids (lactic, succinic, acetic), sugars (maltose, glucose), and ion found in each stage of the lactic acid separation process.

Fermentation broth	Diluate mass (g)	LA (g L ⁻¹)	SA (g L ⁻¹)	AA (g L ⁻¹)	Mal (g L ⁻¹)	Glu (g L ⁻¹)	Cl ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	Na ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	K ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	Ca ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	Mg ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)
MF Retentate	379.60 ± 87.59	39.31 ± 3.21	1.04 ± 0.23	1.34 ± 0.17	23.25 ± 0.96	n.d.	142.5	74.5	5350	812	28.9	7.5
MF Permeate	1569.58 ± 124.78	28.98 ± 2.77	0.41 ± 0.41	1.24 ± 0.18	17.71 ± 0.99	n.d.	160.5	151.2	4560	257	23.9	6.5a
NF Retentate	526	27.3	n.d.	n.d.	27.26	n.d.	173.3	12262	8051	515	56.1	9.9
NF Permeate	1099	16.7	n.d.	n.d.	3.33	n.d.	94.1	114.8	721	20.9	0	0
MED Diluate	444.93 ± 7.39	1.33 ± 0.16	n.d.	n.d.	35.22 ± 12.52	n.d.	35.50 ± 24.61	n.d.	165.00 ± 25.45	n.d.	6.00 ± 0.00	1.50 ± 0.71
MED Concentrate	440.98 ± 0.25	37.18 ± 3.65	n.d.	0.14 ± 0.20	1.26 ± 0.69	n.d.	4592.00 ± 214.96	171.80 ± 21.64	3037.50 ± 67.18	208.00 ± 60.81	17.20 ± 1.27	n.d.
NF_BPED Diluate	466.23 ± 5.06	6.14 ± 0.13	0.07 ± 0.07	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	14.85 ± 0.49	n.d.	49.55 ± 7.85	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
NF_BPED Acid	466.40 ± 2.47	15.46 ± 0.30	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	411.55 ± 222.53	216.90 ± 16.69	90.55 ± 30.33	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
NF_BPED Base	466.25 ± 1.70	1.04 ± 0.31	0.07 ± 0.07	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	48.65 ± 6.29	15.85 ± 1.34	513.00 ± 67.88	15.40 ± 4.10	1.50 ± 2.12	n.d.
MED_BPED Diluate	452.83 ± 30.16	4.49 ± 0.39	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	22.45 ± 2.19	14.15 ± 7.99	126.65 ± 8.98	2.45 ± 3.46	n.d.	n.d.
MED_BPED Acid	452.90 ± 29.42	19.24 ± 2.55	n.d.	n.d.	0.56 ± 0.42	n.d.	3291.50 ± 1009.04	142.10 ± 25.60	348.50 ± 146.37	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
MED_BPED Base	451.45 ± 33.52	0.81 ± 0.03	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	286.40 ± 224.86	30.50 ± 1.56	2600.00 ± 70.71	103.05 ± 4.31	14.40 ± 2.26	5.00 ± 0.70

Fig. 3. Lactic acid recovery and purity as yields for process A: microfiltration (MF)-Nanofiltration (NF)-Bipolar Electrodes (BPED), and for process B: microfiltration (MF)-Monopolar electrodes (MED)-Bipolar Electrodes (BPED).

Table 7

Energy consumption for the pre-purification process, and the two proposed downstream processes, A: microfiltration (MF)-Nanofiltration (NF)-Bipolar Electrodes (BPED), and B: microfiltration (MF)-Monopolar electrodes (MED)-Bipolar Electrodes (BPED).

	Membrane Process	Initial mass diluate (g)	ΔEC_d (mS cm ⁻¹)	Exp. Time (h)	Electrical energy (Wh)	Pumping energy (Wh)	Specific energy demand (kWh m ⁻³)
Process A	MF	1304 ± 81.99	16.453 ± 1.351	3.33	-	0.137 ± 0.01	0.106
	NF	660	1.8	0.83	-	0.943	1.416
	NF, pH 2.8						
	BPED	466.23 ± 5.06	1.44 ± 0.32	0.38 ± 0.14	5.61 ± 2.47	0.30 ± 0.11	12.03 ± 5.17
Process B	MED	444.93 ± 7.39	12.81 ± 1.05	1.17 ± 0.13	14.46 ± 1.78	0.61 ± 0.07	32.56 ± 4.58
	MED_BPED	452.83 ± 30.16	11.10 ± 0.47	0.66 ± 0.05	12.86 ± 0.32	0.51 ± 0.04	28.45 ± 1.20

36-37 compartment was measured to be $81.10 \pm 1.39\%$. In contrast, for process B, the highest ion removal efficiencies were observed for Cl^- , K^+ , and Na^+ ions, with removal rates of $99.28 \pm 1.39\%$, $99.25 \pm 0.75\%$, and $97.97 \pm 0.11\%$, respectively. The lowest ion removal efficiency was recorded for SO_4^{2-} , which reached $88.96 \pm 6.04\%$.

38-39 of lactic acid in process B was higher compared to process A, with a 1.18-fold increase in lactic acid removal. Previous studies have shown that the application of NF technology yields a solution free of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} [4], while MED removed only Mg^{2+} , potentially due to lower atomic weight. The residual Ca^{2+} concentration in the MED concentrate was 17.20 ± 1.27 , thus higher than the recommended concentration of 10 mg L^{-1} .

40 could evolve to be a problem because calcium can precipitate on the bipolar membranes forming an insoluble $Ca(OH)_2$ layer. Finally, after completing the downstream process K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , were fully separated from lactic acid and transported to the base compartment. The main contaminants were $Cl^- > SO_4^{2-} > Na^+$ for Process A and $Cl^- > Na^+ > SO_4^{2-}$ for Process B. It should be highlighted that NaOH was used to set the initial pH of the fermentation broth from 6.5 to 4.0 and 2.8, for MED and NF, respectively.

41 Additionally, measurements of the removal of proteins, phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), and ammonium (NH_4^+) compounds should have been considered for improving the understanding of lactic acid purity. However, it was a limitation of this study that these parameters were not considered.

42-43 Considering the results obtained from a previous laboratory-scale study [4] the removal of 20% nitrogen and 25% phosphorus compounds was detected after the pre-purification process, including centrifugation, ultrafiltration, and activated carbon treatment. Following the pre-purification step 59–61% of nitrogen, and 80–82% of phosphorus were rejected when NF was applied. Another study conducted by Alexandri et al. [1] showed that 39.9–77.5% total nitrogen and

98.8% total phosphorus were rejected after the application of an MF and an NF step, depending on the characteristics of the initial feed. Another study by Knežević et al. [14] comparing ion removal from waste fermentation effluent, comparing NF, MED, and IEX for the recovery of sulfuric acid studied the permeability of NH_4^+ and PO_4^{3-} . According to this research the concentration of NH_4^+ was reduced 1.42- to 2.74-times, applying NF, depending on the characteristics of the membrane. On the contrary, the NH_4^+ concentration was increased by 1.55-times, when applying MED. In the BPED step the excess NH_4^+ is collected to the base compartment creating ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH). The concentration of PO_4^{3-} was also decreased by 1.19- to 1.38-fold when applying NF, and increased by 1.53- to 1.60-fold when running MED. PO_4^{3-} would be transferred to the acid compartment, during a BPED, creating phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4).

Previous studies have been conducted (Table 8) on the downstream of lactic acid deriving from the fermentation of residual streams [1,4,24]. In a study separating lactic acid from municipal biopulp [4], ion exchange (IE) technology or a combination of IE and NF were used. The pre-purification step, which was centrifugation and ultrafiltration, led to complete color removal. Furthermore, 80% of lactic acid was recovered through IE. Additionally, the NF step before IE resulted in 73–74% lactic acid recovery and 75–76% removal of divalent ions. Vacuum distillation was used to convert lactate to lactic acid and the overconcentration of the final product. In another study conducted by Neu et al. [24], several separation technologies, including NF, dialysis, a softening step, MED, BPED, decolorization and distillation, were used for the separation of lactic acid from a fermentation broth derived by coffee mucilage. This combination led to a 38.2% lactic acid recovery and 99.8% purity at the end of the process. Finally, Alexandri et al. [1] applied MF and NF as primary separation steps of lactic acid from a fermentation broth

Table 8

Comparison of study findings with previous literature regarding downstream processes for the separation and purification of lactic acid from heterogeneous fermentation substrates. Where ED: electrodialysis; IEX: ion exchange chromatography; LA: lactic acid, Lab: Laboratory; MF: microfiltration; NF: nanofiltration; n.r.: not reported; VD: vacuum distillation.

References	Scale	Feed	Separation technology	LA recovery (%)	LA purity (%)	Final LA (g L ⁻¹)
Neu et al. [24]	Pilot	Coffee mucilage	Filtration+ ED+ IEX+ Distillation	38.20	n.r.	930
Pleissner et al. [27]	Pilot	Restaurant food waste	Filtration+ ED+ IEX+ Distillation	38.00	n.r.	702
Alexandri et al. [1]	Pilot	Glucose Acid whey Sugar bread Crust bread	MF NF	78.5–100 77.6–97.5	44.2–77.6	29.7–76.6
Alvarado-Morales et al. [4]	Lab	Municipal biopulp	Filtration+ IEX+ VD Filtration+ NF+ IEX+ VD	75.70 65.00	72.5 82.5	12.12 10.39
Case study	Lab	Candy-waste & digestate	Process A Process B	26.00 61.00	95 82	114

produced by sugar and crust bread. They achieved high lactic acid recovery ranging between 2.5% and 22.4% after NF, despite the decreased purity of 77.6%. In these studies, the energy demand of the processes was not reported. In the present study, 26% recovery and 95% purity were reported for process A, and 61% recovery with 82% purity were achieved for process B. For processes A and B, the SEC was 13.55 and 61.12 kWh m⁻³, respectively.

Diluate volumes, EC of the diluate, and removal efficiencies were in a similar range for all three MED rounds (Table 9, Table S2). However, it is visible that during the second and third fed-batch, the total energy consumption was approximately 33–44% lower than within the first step. The higher EC value in the concentrate at the beginning of the MED batch reduces the stack's total resistance, and process efficiency is thus increased.

4.3. MED application for concentrating lactic acid

Fed-batch MED experiments were conducted to increase the final lactic acid concentration. The experiments were conducted with a model solution at pH 4.0 (Table 8, Fig. 4) to test if and how much lactic acid can be concentrated. After repeating MED three times, lactic acid concentration reached 2.31 times higher concentration than the initial solution, reaching up to 114.88 g L⁻¹ (Fig. 4). In a previous study conducted on the purification of organic acids utilizing electrodialysis processes (Q. [33] a final lactic acid concentration of 153 g L⁻¹ was achieved, starting from 27.5 g L⁻¹. The strategy applied was a multistage batch of three repetitions, where the volume ratio between diluate and concentrate was increased up to 1:10.

Table 9

Energy consumption during the different stages of the fed-batch monopolar electrodialysis for the over-concentration of lactic acid.

Step	EC concentrate (mS cm ⁻¹)		EC diluate (mS cm ⁻¹)		Exp. time (h)	Total Energy Demand (Wh)
	Initial	final	initial	final		
step1_A	0.14	14.7	12.91	0.33	1.04	10.2
step2_A	14.32	22.44	10.82	0.31	0.89	7.02
step3_A	21.9	28.51	10.87	0.34	0.82	6.87
step1_B	1.17	14.05	13.07	0.34	1.16	10.48
step2_B	13.01	23.09	12.75	0.34	0.93	7.04
step3_B	22.55	28.94	12.64	0.3	0.78	6.03

Fig. 4. Electric conductivity and lactic acid concentration variations after three stages of fed-batch monopolar electrodialysis for lactic acid over-concentration.

4.4. Choice of process route and future process optimization

The choice of the process routes depends on process and product requirements. Although the energy demand during single-step MED was higher than for NF; the higher recovery rates are a valid reason to suggest process route B for the downstream treatment of lactic acid-containing solutions. Developing a fed-batch ED process, where lactic acid remains in the retentate can be recycled, increases the overall yield and decreases the total energy demand [10]. This has been shown in the multiple concentration experiments where energy demand decreased with the number of batches treated to the lower total resistance in the ED stage.

48 suggested concept includes pre-treatment with MF, pre-concentration with MED in fed-batch operation, and conversions of lactate to lactic acid using BPED. To ensure ion retention, implementing an IE step before BPED would probably be beneficial for process safety. 49 base (NaOH) stream produced from BPED can be used as a pH control agent to reduce the need for fresh NaOH, resulting in lower upstream process cost [13]. Finally, the additional water obtained from BPED dilute can be used for substrate pre-treatment in the upstream process, e.g. for dilution of the initial solution before MF filtration.

If NF is chosen, comprehensive trials of NF membranes with different properties are proposed [8].

Overall, these approaches can improve the efficiency and sustainability of the downstream process of lactic acid, making its production more economically viable and environmentally friendly.

5. Conclusions

Challenges such as low product purity, low recovery, and high energy demand should be addressed to develop a lactic acid biorefinery. This study emphasizes the importance of regulating parameters such as pH to optimize membrane technologies for the desired bio-product. In the case of lactic acid, pH values of 2.8 and 4.0 were the most suitable for separation via NF and MED, respectively. Additionally, Process B where MED was combined with BPED, resulted in a 1.09-fold increase in lactic acid recovery compared to Process A, where NF was combined with BPED. However, process B showed a specific energy demand 4.51 times higher than process A, and a 6.02-fold higher number of ions remained in the final solution. Finally, the application of fed-batch MED increased lactic acid concentration from 43.70 to 114 g L⁻¹, which is promising for industrial applications. According to our results, downstream treatment by MF, multiple MED and BPED is proposed. Overall, this study provides an optimized strategy for the downstream processing of lactic acid derived from microbial fermentation of heterogeneous residual streams with high sugar content.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Eleftheria Papadopoulou: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Mayuki Cabrera-Gonzalez:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Daniela Reif:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Amal Ahmed:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Panagiotis Tsapekos:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Irini Angelidaki:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Michael Harasek:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests. Irini Angelidaki, Michael Harasek reports financial support was provided by Europe Horizons.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 – Marie Skłodowska-Curie research and innovation program (grant agreement No 860477). The authors would like to express their gratitude to Matthias Hainz, Laura Daza-Serna, Camila Cabeza, Alexandra Nastouli, and Thomas Jung for their invaluable assistance in the lab work and sample analysis. Furthermore, the authors would like to acknowledge and thank the lab personnel of the Institute for Water Quality management for their valuable support during chemical analysis. The authors acknowledge also TU Wien Bibliothek for financial support through its Open Access Funding Program.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jece.2023.110881](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.110881).

References

- [1] M. Alexandri, R. Schneider, J. Venus, Membrane technologies for lactic acid separation from fermentation broths derived from renewable resources, *Membranes* 8 (4) (2018), <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes8040094>.
- [2] M. Alexandri, D. Hübner, R. Schneider, A. Fröhling, J. Venus, Towards efficient production of highly optically pure D-lactic acid from lignocellulosic hydrolysates using newly isolated lactic acid bacteria, *N. Biotechnol.* 72 (May) (2022) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2022.08.003>.
- [3] L. Alibardi, T.F. Astrup, F. Asunis, W.P. Clarke, G. De Gioannis, P. Dessì, P.N. L. Lens, M.C. Lavagnolo, L. Lombardi, A. Muntioni, A. Pivato, A. Poletini, R. Pomi, A. Rossi, A. Spagni, D. Spiga, Organic waste biorefineries: Looking towards implementation, *Waste Manag.* 114 (2020) 274–286, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.07.010>.
- [4] M. Alvarado-Morales, M. Kuglarz, P. Tsapekos, I. Angelidaki, Municipal biopulp as substrate for lactic acid production focusing on downstream processing, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2) (2021), 105136, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105136>.
- [5] R. Alves de Oliveira, A. Komesu, C.E. Vaz Rossell, R. Maciel Filho, Challenges and opportunities in lactic acid bioprocess design—from economic to production aspects, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 133 (2018) 219–239, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2018.03.003>.
- [6] R. Alves De Oliveira, M. Alexandri, A. Komesu, J. Venus, C.E. Vaz Rossell, R. Maciel Filho, Current advances in separation and purification of second-generation lactic acid, *Sep. Purif. Rev.* 49 (2) (2020) 159–175, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15422119.2019.1590412>.
- [7] M. Bédas, G. Tanguy, A. Dolivet, S. Méjean, F. Gaucheron, G. Garric, G. Senard, R. Jeantet, P. Schuck, Nanofiltration of lactic acid whey prior to spray drying: scaling up to a semi-industrial scale, *Lwt* 79 (2017) 355–360, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2017.01.061>.
- [8] M. Cabrera-González, A. Ahmed, K. Maamo, M. Salem, C. Jordan, M. Harasek, Evaluation of nanofiltration membranes for pure lactic acid permeability, *Membranes* 12 (3) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes12030302>.
- [9] Y. Cao, X. Chen, S. Feng, Y. Wan, J. Luo, Nanofiltration for decolorization: membrane fabrication, applications and challenges, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 59 (45) (2020) 19858–19875, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.0c04277>.
- [10] G.Q. Chen, F.I.I. Eschbach, M. Weeks, S.L. Gras, S.E. Kentish, Removal of lactic acid from acid whey using electrodialysis, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 158 (2016) 230–237, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2015.12.016>.
- [11] Climate Change: Global Temperature | NOAA Climate.gov. (n.d.). Retrieved March 8, 2023, from <https://www.climate.gov/news-features/understanding-climate/climate-change-global-temperature>.
- [12] L. Handoyo, A.K. Wardani, D. Regina, C. Bella, M.T.A.P. Kresnowati, I.G. Wenten, Electro-membrane processes for organic acid recovery, *RSC Adv.* 9 (14) (2019) 7854–7869, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RA09227C>.
- [13] S. Jantasee, M. Kienberger, N. Mungma, M. Siebenhofer, Potential and assessment of lactic acid production and isolation – a review, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 92 (12) (2017) 2885–2893, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.5237>.

- [14] K. Knezevic, E. Saracevic, J. Krampe, N. Kreuzinger, Comparison of ion removal from waste fermentation effluent by nanofiltration, electro dialysis and ion exchange for a subsequent sulfuric acid recovery, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 10 (5) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.108423>.
- [15] A. Komesu, J. Allan Rocha de Oliveira, L. Helena da Silva Martins, M. Regina Wolf Maciel, R. Maciel Filho, Lactic acid manufacture, *BioResources* 12 (2) (2017) 4364–4383.
- [16] B. Kumar, N. Bhardwaj, K. Agrawal, V. Chaturvedi, P. Verma, Current perspective on pretreatment technologies using lignocellulosic biomass: an emerging biorefinery concept, *Fuel Process. Technol.* 199 (October 2019) (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2019.106244>.
- [17] H. Kyllönen, J. Heikkinen, J. Ceras, C. Fernandez, O. Porc, A. Grönroos, Membrane-based conceptual design of reuse water production from candy factory wastewater, *Water Sci. Technol.* 84 (6) (2021) 1389–1402, <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2021.326>.
- [18] L. Lange, K.O. Connor, S. Arason, U. Bundgård-Jørgensen, A. Canalis, D. Carrez, J. Gallagher, N. Gøtke, C. Huyghe, B. Jarry, P. Llorente, M. Marinova, L.O. Martins, P. Mengal, P. Paiano, C. Panoutsou, L. Rodrigues, D.B. Stengel, Y. van der Meer, H. Vieira, Developing a sustainable and circular bio-based economy in EU: by partnering across sectors, upscaling and using new knowledge faster, and for the benefit of climate, environment & biodiversity, and people & business, *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 8 (January) (2021) 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2020.619066>.
- [19] C. Li, M. Gao, W. Zhu, N. Wang, X. Ma, C. Wu, Q. Wang, Recent advances in the separation and purification of lactic acid from fermentation broth, *Process Biochem.* 104 (February) (2021) 142–151, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2021.03.011>.
- [20] Y. Li, A. Shahbazi, Fermentation broth using combined ultrafiltration and nanofiltration membranes, *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* 129–132 (1–3) (2006) 985–996.
- [21] J.P. López-Gómez, P. Unger, R. Schneider, J. Venus, From upstream to purification: production of lactic acid from the organic fraction of municipal solid waste, *Waste Biomass.-. Valoriz.* 11 (10) (2020) 5247–5254, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-020-00992-9>.
- [22] Y. Luo, Y. Liu, J. Shen, B. Van der Bruggen, Application of bipolar membrane electro dialysis in environmental protection and resource recovery: a review, *Membranes* 12 (9) (2022) 829, <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes12090829>.
- [23] N. Najid, S. Kouzbou, B. Gourich, Improvement of permeation flux by evaluating the effects of coagulated-humic acids flocs and pH during coagulation-microfiltration hybrid process for water treatment: performance, fouling modeling, specific energy consumption, and processes comparison, *Chem. Eng. Process. - Process. Intensif.* 179 (July) (2022), 109081, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2022.109081>.
- [24] A.K. Neu, D. Pleissner, K. Mehlmann, R. Schneider, G.I. Puerta-Quintero, J. Venus, Fermentative utilization of coffee mucilage using *Bacillus* coagulans and investigation of down-stream processing of fermentation broth for optically pure l(+)-lactic acid production, *Bioresour. Technol.* 211 (2016) 398–405, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.03.122>.
- [25] A. Olszewska-Widdrat, M. Alexandri, J.P. López-Gómez, R. Schneider, M. Mandl, J. Venus, Production and purification of L-lactic acid in lab and pilot scales using sweet sorghum juice, *Fermentation* 5 (2) (2019) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation5020036>.
- [26] E. Papadopoulou, C. Vance, P.S.R. Vallespin, P. Tsapekos, I. Angelidaki, Saccharina latissima, candy-factory waste, and digestate from full-scale biogas plant as alternative carbohydrate and nutrient sources for lactic acid production, *SSRN Electron. J.* 380 (March) (2023), 129078, <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4386841>.
- [27] D. Pleissner, F. Demichelis, S. Mariano, S. Fiore, I.M. Navarro Gutiérrez, R. Schneider, J. Venus, Direct production of lactic acid based on simultaneous saccharification and fermentation of mixed restaurant food waste, *J. Clean. Prod.* 143 (2017) 615–623, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.065>.
- [28] S. Talebi, M. Garthe, F. Roghman, G.Q. Chen, S.E. Kentish, Lactic acid and salt separation using membrane technology, *Membranes* 11 (2) (2021) 1–15, <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes11020107>.
- [29] N.T.H. Thuy, A. Boontawan, Production of very-high purity succinic acid from fermentation broth using microfiltration and nanofiltration-assisted crystallization, *J. Membr. Sci.* 524 (November 2016) (2017) 470–481, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2016.11.073>.
- [30] E.W. Tow, A.L. Hartman, A. Jaworowski, I. Zucker, S. Kum, M. AzadiAghdam, E. R. Blatchley, A. Achilli, H. Gu, G.M. Urper, D.M. Warsinger, Modeling the energy consumption of potable water reuse schemes, *Water Res. X* 13 (2021), 100126, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wroa.2021.100126>.
- [31] A.T. Ubando, C.B. Felix, W.H. Chen, Biorefineries in circular bioeconomy: a comprehensive review, *Bioresour. Technol.* 299 (November 2019) (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2019.122585>.
- [32] United Nations. (n.d.). Population | United Nations. Retrieved March 8, 2023, from <https://www.un.org/en/global-issues/population>.
- [33] Q. Wang, G.Q. Chen, L. Lin, X. Li, S.E. Kentish, Purification of organic acids using electro dialysis with bipolar membranes (EDBM) combined with monovalent anion selective membranes, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 279 (September) (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2021.119739>.
- [34] R. Wang, R.W. Hartel, Confectionery gels: gelling behavior and gel properties of gelatin in concentrated sugar solutions, *Food Hydrocoll.* 124 (PA) (2022), 107132, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2021.107132>.
- [35] S.F. Yuan, T.C. Hsu, C.A. Wang, M.F. Jang, Y.C. Kuo, H.S. Alper, G.L. Guo, W. S. Hwang, Production of optically pure l(+)-lactic acid from waste plywood chips using an isolated thermotolerant enterococcus faecalis SI at a pilot scale, *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 45 (11) (2018) 961–970, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10295-018-2078-5>.
- [36] Z. Zhang, P. Tsapekos, M. Alvarado-Morales, X. Zhu, A. Zervas, C.S. Jacobsen, I. Angelidaki, Enhanced fermentative lactic acid production from source-sorted organic household waste: Focusing on low-pH microbial adaptation and bio-augmentation strategy, *Sci. Total Environ.* 808 (2022), 152129, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152129>.
- [37] J. Zhou, H. Kuang, W. Zhuang, Y. Chen, D. Liu, H. Ying, J. Wu, Application of electro dialysis to extract 5'-ribonucleotides from hydrolysate: Efficient decolorization and membrane fouling, *RSC Adv.* 8 (51) (2018) 29115–29128, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8ra02550a>.
- [38] M. Ziadi, S. M'Hir, A. Aydi, M. Hamdi, A. Al Loman, Bioreactor scale-up and kinetic modeling of lactic acid and biomass production by enterococcus faecalis SLT13 during batch culture on hydrolyzed cheese whey, *J. Chem.* (2020) 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/1236784>.

Separation of lactic acid from fermented residual resources using membrane technology

Papadopoulou, Eleftheria; González, Mayuki Cabrera; Reif, Daniela; Ahmed, Amal; Tsapekos, Panagiotis; Angelidaki, Irini; Harasek, Michael

- | | | |
|----|-------------------------|--------|
| 01 | Eleftheria Papadopoulou | Page 2 |
| | 23/10/2023 16:17 | |
| 02 | Eleftheria Papadopoulou | Page 2 |
| | 23/10/2023 16:17 | |
| 03 | Eleftheria Papadopoulou | Page 2 |
| | 23/10/2023 16:17 | |
| 04 | Eleftheria Papadopoulou | Page 2 |
| | 23/10/2023 16:17 | |
| 05 | Eleftheria Papadopoulou | Page 2 |
| | 23/10/2023 15:30 | |
| 06 | Eleftheria Papadopoulou | Page 2 |
| | 23/10/2023 16:40 | |
| 07 | Eleftheria Papadopoulou | Page 2 |
| | 23/10/2023 15:31 | |
| 08 | Eleftheria Papadopoulou | Page 2 |
| | 23/10/2023 16:40 | |
| 09 | Eleftheria Papadopoulou | Page 2 |
| | 23/10/2023 17:06 | |

10	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 2
	23/10/2023 17:06	
11	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 2
	23/10/2023 17:06	
12	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 2
	23/10/2023 17:07	
13	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 2
	23/10/2023 17:07	
14	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 2
	23/10/2023 15:35	
15	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 4
	23/10/2023 17:38	
16	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:39	
17	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:30	
18	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:31	
19	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:33	
20	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:51	
21	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:35	

22	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:52	
23	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:36	
24	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:38	
25	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 5
	18/10/2023 7:38	
26	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 7:54	
27	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 8:01	
28	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 8:03	
29	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 8:04	
30	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 8:04	
31	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 7:58	
32	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 8:06	
33	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 8:00	

34	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 8:07	
35	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 6
	18/10/2023 8:08	
36	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:13	
37	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:13	
38	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:09	
39	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:09	
40	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:14	
41	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:10	
42	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:11	
43	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:16	
44	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:17	
45	Eleftheria Papadopoulou	Page 7
	18/10/2023 8:18	

46 Eleftheria Papadopoulou

Page 7

18/10/2023 8:12

47 Eleftheria Papadopoulou

Page 8

18/10/2023 8:31

48 Eleftheria Papadopoulou

Page 9

18/10/2023 8:36

49 Eleftheria Papadopoulou

Page 9

18/10/2023 8:37